

Electrical Conduction Mechanisms in Insulators. Part-1. Mica Films

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Electrical conduction of mica films of varying thicknesses (20–50 microns) indicates different conduction mechanisms at different field strengths. At fields 10–20 MV m⁻¹, the current is found to be space-charge limited due to shallow trapping of electrons. Beyond this field (at room temperature) the current does not show a sharp rise as it should be, in the case of an insulator containing shallow traps. This behaviour is attributed to polaron conduction. At higher temperatures the current increases with the field as in the case of an insulator containing shallow traps.

VON Hippel¹ studied the high field conductivity of mica and found that the current is space-charge limited by trapped electrons. Maltsev² obtained an expression for conductivity of the form, $\sigma = \sigma_0 \exp(\beta F^{1/2})$, where F is the electric field, σ_0 and β are constants. Foot and Kazan³ found the current density to be of the form, $j = j_0 \exp(\beta F^{1/2})$ on a sample of thickness 4 nm. McColl and Mead⁴ working on films of green muscovite of thickness greater than 7 nm found that the samples exhibited voltage-current curves suggesting Schottky emission of electrons. They also suggested that the electrons were being injected into polaron states in the insulator. The present work is on thicker films (20–50 μm) of mica (ruby) obtained from Giridih (Bihar).

Experimental

The cell constructed consisted of a sample holder made of two plane and two parallel aluminium disc electrodes, one of which being detachable. The fixed electrode with a larger diameter (2.5 cm) was located below the detachable electrode (dia 1.5 cm). The specimen was cut to the same size as the lower electrode so as to minimise the effects due to surface conduction. The detachable electrode was rigidly connected to the central leg of a spherometer. Thus the electrode could be moved up and down and its displacement with respect to the fixed electrode measured. The leads were of the screened type, one leading to the fixed electrode and the other to the moveable one. Bakelite pillars with teflon washers at either end, supported the mechanism for the moving electrode. Special guard rings of teflon isolated the two electrodes. A glass tube surrounded the lower electrode and was ground; the upper electrode moved freely within the glass tube. The

entire cell was kept in a desiccator with silica gel. A DC power supply was fabricated in the laboratory.

The samples of mica of varying thickness (20–50 μm) were screen-printed with silver and used in the cell after cutting to the appropriate size. The silver on the top was etched away to the dimension of the upper electrode with the help of concentrated nitric acid. The material was then cleaned thoroughly with conductivity water and allowed to dry in an air-oven at 100°.

Results and Discussion

The steady state currents were recorded at different voltages. The characteristics could be divided into three distinct regions where (i) Ohm's law is obeyed, (ii) there is a sharp rise in current and (iii) the slope decreases. The $J-V$ curves were plotted (Fig. 1). The slope of the second region indicates a square-law dependence. Mott and Gurney⁵ equation for a trap-free insulator is

$$J = 9\mu\epsilon\epsilon_0 V^2 / 8s^3$$

where J is the current density, μ the mobility, ϵ the dielectric constant, ϵ_0 the permittivity of the free space, V the applied voltage and s the thickness of the sample. The equation gives a large value of current than the observed value by an order of 10⁵.

Considering the realistic case of an insulator containing traps, Rose⁶ calculated that a large fraction of the injected space charge condenses in the traps, which means that the free carrier density is much lower than that in a trap-free insulator. Traps lower the mobility of carriers and hence the magnitude of space-charge limited conduction. The value of the fraction by which the drift mobility is reduced is determined by the number and the

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log J$ vs $\log V$ for mica

depth of traps. As the occupancy of traps is a function of temperature, the space charge limited conduction is a function of temperature.

If the insulator contains N_t shallow traps positioned at energy E_t below the conduction band, the ratio of free to trapped charge,

$$\theta = \frac{N_c}{N_t} \exp(-N_t/KT)$$

Hence for an insulator containing shallow traps,

$$J = \frac{9}{8} \mu \epsilon \epsilon_0 \frac{V^2}{s^3} \theta$$

Assuming N_c and $N_t \approx 10^{18}/\text{cc}$ and $\theta = 10^{-5}$ it gives a value of $E_t = 0.251$ eV at room temperature. The plot of $\log \theta$ vs $1/T$ was found nearly linear. The value of E_t obtained from the plot is 0.28 eV. Further, the values of slopes obtained from $(\log J - \log V)$ plots are nearly of the same order for the different samples used (Table 1). This confirms the square-law dependence on voltage. The values of $V^2/s^3 J$ prove the cube-dependence on the thickness.

TABLE I

Thickness μ	Slope in region (a)	Slope in region (b)	Slope in region (c)	$(V/s^3 J) \times 10^{23} (\text{V/cm})^3 \text{A}^{-1}$
20	0.98	2.14	0.71	1.17
40	0.97	1.98	0.69	1.22
50	1.00	2.01	0.67	1.21

In region (3), there is a decrease in the slope of the $(\log J - \log V)$ characteristics. The reason for the drop in conductivity may be due to the interaction between electrons and phonons. This may lead to the distortion of the material around a trapped or a free carrier, thus lowering the energy leading to lower conduction. Using the expression obtained by Mott and Davis⁴ for the lowering of energy of the electron,

$$\Delta W = \frac{1}{2} \frac{e^2}{K_p r_0}$$

where, e is the electronic charge and r_0 the radius of the trapping centre K_p is given by $1/K_p = 1/K_\infty - 1/K$, where K_∞ is the high frequency dielectric constant. Taking K_∞ for the samples as n^2 (n being the refractive index), K_p is calculated to be 3.7 and $r_0 = 51.8 \mu\text{m}$ leads to a lowering of energy of 0.37 eV.

Also, for a carrier in the conduction band of a crystal, if the interaction energy between the carriers and phonons is strong in comparison with the band width, then small polarons may form. This behaves like a particle with enhanced mass at low temperature. At high temperatures it moves by thermal hopping.

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